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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In family medicine practice, the correct definition of normal growth, frequency of follow-up and short stature enables the correct cases to be referred to pediatric endocrinology clinics (Nichols, 2025). This study aims to evaluate the approaches of family physicians to normal growth and short stature.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted through a questionnaire sent electronically to family physicians, SAHU residents and family medicine specialists. The questionnaire, which was answered by 165 people in total, consisted of 25 questions, 7 of which were about demographic data and the rest were about evaluating the approach to normal growth and short stature. Participants were divided into three groups according to their years of professional experience: Group 1 with <5 years (34), Group 2 between 5-10 years (58), and Group 3 with >10 years (73), and were evaluated in terms of their approaches to growth and short stature.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 37 ± 8.1 years, 62% (102) were male, 26% (43) were SAHU residents, 54% (89) were family physicians, and 20% (33) were family medicine specialists. All participants agreed that normal growth monitoring has an important place in family medicine practice. In growth velocity monitoring, only 46% (75) of the participants stated that the frequency of evaluation should be every six months. For the definition of short stature, 57% (94) of the participants thought that the child should be <2.3p for age and gender. Only 38% (63) thought that children with a height >2.3p, who did not lose their height percentile during follow-up, who did not have findings suggesting systemic disease or who did not show characteristics such as growth below their genetic potential, did not require additional evaluation. When the participants were evaluated according to their professional years, 98% of Group 3, 100% of Group 2 and 85% of Group 1 agreed that children with a height <2.3p had short stature and should be referred to a pediatric endocrinologist, and there was a statistically significant difference between the groups ($p:0.001$).

Conclusion: Although the participants' approaches to normal growth monitoring are appropriate, it is seen that the level of knowledge about growth monitoring intervals, the definition of short stature, and the fact that height is normal when there are no other pathological findings when it is >2.3p should be increased (Padilla & Rogol, 2025). It is seen that the physicians in Group 2 are more knowledgeable in some areas, although there is no major difference.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Short stature, growth monitoring, family medicine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

The authors have no conflicts of interest to report and no financial interests to disclose.

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